

Physico-Chemical Studies of Zinc (II)-N-Phenyl-n-Butyrohydroxamate Complex

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In the present investigation the thermodynamic stability constants of Zn(II)-N-phenyl n-butyrohydroxamic acid [*p*-(*n*)-BHA] complex have been studied by *p*H titration technique in 50 volume % aqueous dioxane media at 25° and 35°. The effect of inert salt on the stability of complex was studied. Stability constants of the complex are found by Bjerrum's method¹ and calculations were made by algebraic solution of the simultaneous equations^{2,3}.

From the knowledge of these constants at two temperatures the standard thermodynamic quantities have been calculated.

EXPERIMENTAL AND DISCUSSION

Preparation of Zinc Perchlorate : To 30 ml. of 2*M* perchloric acid was added a little excess of zinc oxide. The solution was gently boiled, cooled and filtered through a sintered glass crucible of porosity GX₄. The *p*H of the filtrate was 6.78. Zinc content of the solution was determined⁴.

A Radiometer *p*H meter Model *p*HM4C equipped with a Radiometer glass electrode G-200-B and a calomel electrode K-100 was employed for *p*H measurements.

(A) *Stability Constants* : *p*H titration method using Calvin Bjerrum technique^{1,5}. the following sets were prepared.

(i) 0.01*M* HClO₄ and 0.0100*M* *p*-(*n*)-BHA in 50 volume % dioxane.

(ii) 0.01*M* HClO₄, 0.0100*M* *p*-(*n*)-BHA and 0.001*M* Zn(ClO₄)₂ in 50 volume % dioxane.

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pH titrations were carried out in nitrogen atmosphere. \bar{n} values were evaluated⁶ from the horizontal distance on Fig. 1 between the reference curve I and curve II determined the presence of the metal ion. \bar{n} values thus obtained were plotted against pCh^- for getting the formation curve (Fig. 2).

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

(B) *Thermodynamic Stability Constants*: These were determined by following the method of Bjerrum-Calvin as applied by Van Uitert⁷ *et al.* to mixed aqueous solvents. Calculations have been made by solving simultaneous equations² adapting the procedure as applied by Goldberg³.

Into a three necked titration cell which accommodated a glass electrode, a limb of salt bridge to make the contact with calomel electrode, a burette and a inlet of nitrogen, 25 ml. dioxane solution of 0.02M p -(n)-BHA, 10 ml. of 0.01M zinc perchlorate and 15 ml. of water were added. Next, the cell was thermostated at 25° or 35°. The solution was titrated with a carbonate free 0.1M KOH which was also prepared in 50 volume % dioxane. After each addition the pH meter reading was noted.

The same titration was repeated with adjusting the ionic strength 0.01, 0.05 or 0.1M by sodium perchlorate.

The activity coefficient needed for the present investigation were obtained by the interpolation of the Harned and Owen's⁸ data. The thermodynamic ionization constants, pK_a is at 50 volume percent dioxane water media at 25° and 35° are 11.49 and 11.33°, respectively.

The value of stability constant are given in Tables 1 and 2. The thermodynamic quantities are given in Table 3.

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TABLE 1

Stability constants of Zn(II) p-(n)-BHA

pH	\bar{n}	pCh ⁻	log K* ₁	log K* ₂
5.50	0.43	7.95		
5.75	0.56	7.71		
6.00	0.71	7.47		
6.50	1.12	6.98	7.85	6.40
7.00	1.33	6.49		
7.50	1.48	6.00		
8.00	1.68	5.51		
9.00	1.84	4.42		

K* Thermodynamic Constants; obtained after applying the activity correction.

TABLE 2

Temp. °C	μ	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₁ K ₂
25	—	7.85	6.40	14.25
25	0.01M (HClO ₄)	7.85	6.40	14.25
25	0.01M (NaClO ₄)	7.86	6.38	14.24
25	0.05M (NaClO ₄)	7.87	6.39	14.26
25	0.1 M (NaClO ₄)	7.83	6.41	14.24
35	—	7.79	6.30	14.09
35	0.01M (NaClO ₄)	7.78	6.29	14.07

TABLE 3

Thermodynamic Constants of Zn²⁺ p-(n)-BHA Complex

Constant	ΔF°	$-\Delta S^\circ$	ΔH°
log K ₁	10.72 (11.09)	26.1 (27.3)	2.95
log K ₂	8.74 (8.88)	14.7 (15.2)	4.21

Remarks : (i) Values given in parentheses are at 35°.
(ii) ΔF° and ΔH° are in Kcals. mole⁻¹;
 ΔS° is in Cal. deg.⁻¹ mole⁻¹.

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